

calculated for: Th, 28.57; C, 50.24; H, 2.46; N, 6.89%). The ir spectrum of the thorium chelate indicated the absence of characteristic absorptions for OH and COOH groups. However, the strong absorption of the ligand at 1700 cm^{-1} due to γ ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) is shifted to lower frequencies in the chelate and appears at 1600 cm^{-1} . A strong band at 1450 cm^{-1} ($\text{N}=\text{N}$) is shifted to 1400 cm^{-1} in the complex. These shifts towards lower frequencies show that $\text{N}=\text{N}$ and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ are involved in bond formation. The TGA data also support 1 : 2 complex.

Estimation of thorium in monazite: Powdered monazite sand was converted into a mixture of thorium and rare earth sulphates by heating with concentrated H_2SO_4 . Accurately weighed quantities of Travancore monazite were digested with 3-4 times its weight of concentrated H_2SO_4 for 4 h at $200\text{--}250^\circ$. The mass was extracted with ice-cold water. Thorium and rare earth metals were precipitated by oxalic acid. Reprecipitation was carried out. The precipitate was dissolved in concentrated HNO_3 and the excess acid evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in water and acetate-acetic acid buffer was added to adjust the pH at 5.3 and Th was estimated with CPAN according to the procedure detailed above. Similar experiments was conducted using fresh samples of monazite. Th is precipitated as iodate by standard procedure⁷. Thorium iodate is converted into oxalate by using oxalic acid. Finally, thorium oxalate is ignited to ThO_2 , dried and weighed.

ThO_2 contents in monazite obtained through these two methods are comparable: iodate method, 8.99%; and CPAN method, 9.00%.

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Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Molybdenum with Benzyltriethylammonium Chloride

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A number of quaternary ammonium salts have been reported to find application in the determination of a large number of metal ions in small

concentration in solution. Yoshimura and Ueno¹ used benzyltrimethylphenylammonium chloride in the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II), iron(III), copper(II) and molybdenum(V) in SCN^- solutions. The same reagent was employed for the gravimetric determination of platinum² and extractive spectrophotometric determination of bismuth³ and palladium⁴. Benzyltriethylammonium chloride in SCN^- solution reacts with many metallic ions with the formation of coloured precipitate. The present work describes a highly sensitive and selective method for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of molybdenum(V) in trace concentrations using benzyltriethylammonium chloride as reagent and 1,2-dichloroethane as the extracting solvent.

Experimental

A Hilger Uvispek photoelectric spectrophotometer with matched quartz cells of 1 cm optical path was used.

The stock solution of molybdenum was prepared from molybdenum trioxide (A.R.) and was standardised by known method⁵. Test solutions of lower concentration were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock. The reagent, benzyltriethylammonium chloride, was prepared⁶ by refluxing for 1 h a mixture of ethyl acetate, dimethylformamide, triethylamine and benzylchloride. A 0.01 M solution of benzyltriethylammonium chloride, a 3 M solution of potassium thiocyanate and a saturated solution (18 M) of thiourea were prepared in distilled water. All chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Procedure: An aliquot of the solution containing 4-80 μg of molybdenum was made acidic with 18 M H_2SO_4 (2 ml). To this the thiourea solution (8 ml), the potassium thiocyanate solution (4 ml) and then the benzyltriethylammonium chloride solution (5 ml) were added. The total volume was made up to 25 ml with distilled water. The resulting solution after having mixed with 1,2-dichloroethane (20 ml) was shaken for 3 min, and the organic layer separated. Absorbance of the extract was measured at 465 nm against the pure solvent. Amount of molybdenum in unknown solutions was calculated from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Benzyltriethylammonium chloride (QCl) reacts with the SCN^- -complex of molybdenum(V) yielding the ion-pair $\text{Q}^+ [\text{Mo}(\text{SCN})_6]^-$ in the form of an orange-yellow precipitate. The ion-pair is completely extractable into 1,2-dichloroethane and the extract absorbs maximum at 465 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 0.2-4.0 ppm of molybdenum. The reagent blank shows no absorption at this wave length. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are $1.79 \times 10^4\text{ l mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0053\text{ }\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

The complex exhibits constant and maximum absorption provided the acidity of the aqueous layer be maintained at 1-2 *M* with respect to sulphuric acid. The role of thiourea is mainly in reducing molybdenum(VI) to molybdenum(V) and in increasing the rate of formation and stability of the coloured complex⁷. A thiourea concentration below 0.13 *M* in the aqueous phase resulted in the lowering of absorbance while higher concentrations were without any significant effect. Effect of thiocyanate concentration on the absorbance was studied by using potassium thiocyanate solution of varying concentrations. It was found that concentrations below 0.18 *M* and beyond 0.88 *M* in the aqueous layer with respect to potassium thiocyanate produced low values of absorbance. As regards reagent concentration, 5 ml of a 0.01 *M* solution of benzyltriethylammonium chloride was adequate for complete extraction of the complex for the given range of molybdenum concentration. Reagent concentration below 0.003 *M* in the aqueous phase resulted in the decrease in absorbance while higher concentration could produce no change in the colour intensity.

Effect of foreign ions : A number of representative ions were examined for their interference in the determination of molybdenum by the recommended procedure. The tolerance limit (Table 1) was set at the amount required to cause less than 3 per cent error in the recovery of molybdenum by restricting the higher limit of foreign ion concentration to 1000-fold excess (w/w) to that of molybdenum.

The present method proves very rapid and simple, and provides excellent recovery of molybdenum in micro-quantities in presence of most of the common ions. Standard deviation and coefficient of variation as obtained from the absorbance of 2 ppm of molybdenum were 0.0015 and 0.416%, respectively. The method, further deserves special mention of its selectivity in the

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF FOREIGN IONS ON EXTRACTION OF MOLYBDENUM

Mo taken = 40 μ g			
Ions added	Tolerance limit mg	Ions added	Tolerance limit mg
Cu ^{II}	4	Mn ^{II}	40
Ag ^I	20	Mn ^{VII}	40
Au ^{III}	40	Fe ^{II}	2.8
Zn ^{II}	12	Fe ^{III}	2
Cd ^{II}	0.32	Co ^{II}	40
Hg ^{II}	32	Ni ^{II}	40
Sn ^{II}	0.20	Rh ^{III}	40
Sn ^{IV}	0.80	Pd ^{II}	0.4
Pb ^{II}	0.80	Pt ^{IV}	8
As ^{III}	40	Fluoride	40
As ^V	40	Bromide	40
Sb ^{III}	40	Iodide	40
Bj ^{III}	40	Thiosulphate	0.4
V ^V	4	Oxalate	40
Cr ^{III}	40	Citrate	40
Cr ^{VI}	32	Tartrate	40
W ^{VI}	1	EDTA	40

sense that interference from foreign ions is much less than that in case of other existing methods for the determination of molybdenum.

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